

Maximization of Scattering Arrangements Equivalent to Reaction Balance?

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In regular statistical mechanics, the idea of “maximizing” the number of physical arrangements of particles with different energies leads to both Shannon’s entropy and the canonical distribution (1). This “maximization of arrangements”, it seems, is treated as a fundamental idea of nature. In a series of notes, we argued that the equilibrium distribution for general cases as well as for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case may be obtained from a time reversal balance of elastic two body collisions. In a previous note (2), we argued one may map collisions (e.g. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$) into $M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)$ where m_1 is the number of reactions of particles with energy m_1 . (For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, then number of reactions is proportional to the number of particles, but this is not the general case.) If e_1 and e_2 appear next to each other in the factorial arrangement, they may react. In (2), however, we did not argue why one needs to “maximize” the scattering arrangements. Instead, we showed maximization leads to the same result as reaction balance. In this note, we try to investigate why maximization is the same reaction balance.

Scattering Probability Versus Particle Number Distribution

Time reversal elastic scattering balance is based on the idea that the probability for a forward scattering reactions equals that for time-reversed reaction. Thus, $e_1+e_2 \rightarrow e_3+e_4$ has the same probability as $e_3+e_4 \rightarrow e_1+e_2$. This ensures conservation of energy, overall particle number and particle number distribution. It should be noted, however, that one deals with scattering probabilities, written as $g(f((e-u)/T))$. Only in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case does one have $g(f)=f$. Thus: $g(f(e_1)) g(f(e_2)) = g(f(e_3)) g(f(e_4))$. Taking \ln and matching with energy conservation yields the general result: $\ln(g(f(e_i))) = -(e_i-u)/T$. Thus, there is “physics” due to the scattering probability g (e.g. for fermions $g=f/(1-f)$, for bosons $g=f/(1+f)$) and also a physical balancing. No new principle such as the “maximization of scattering arrangements”, entropy or partition functions is needed.

Nevertheless, historically much emphasis has been placed on factorial arrangements and their maximization (1). Thus, it would be good to link maximization of scattering arrangements to a reaction balance.

Maximization of Scattering Arrangements

In (1), the canonical distribution (and also Shannon’s entropy) result from the maximization of :

$M! / (m_1! 2! \dots)$ ((1)) Here m_1 is the number of reactions of a particle with energy e_1

(In statistical mechanics texts m_1 is taken to be the number of particles with energy e_1 , but this is the Maxwell-Boltzmann case for which the number of particles and the scattering probability are proportional.)

The question we ask is why should one maximize ((1)) and what does this have to do with a time reversal elastic scattering balance?

As a first step, one may consider how elastic scattering reactions are mapped into the factorial scheme ((1)). For two particles with energies e_1 and e_2 to scatter, they must be physically present at the same point in space. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, this probability is taken as $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ i.e. one multiplies two particle densities. This seems to have nothing to do with factorials. If one maps 3-space into a line (similar to mapping a matrix into a vector), one may argue that if a particle with e_1 is "next" to a particle with e_2 , they may react, otherwise not. (Note: m_1 is not the number of particles with energy e_1 , but the number of reactions a particle with e_1 may make.) (This holds at a time t_1 .) Thus, a factorial scheme such as ((1)) may describe various physical arrangements and the scattering that will occur based on such arrangements. This, however, does not explain why the number of arrangements should be maximized.

Next consider the scattering balance situation $e_1+e_2 \rightarrow \leftarrow e_i + e_j$ and imagine that one does not have equilibrium e.g. there are too many e_1 and e_2 particles. Then, physically as the system moves toward equilibrium, some e_1 and e_2 particles disappear and some e_i and e_j are created. Thus, $f(e_1)$ and $f(e_2)$ decrease and $f(e_i)$ and $f(e_j)$ increase, i.e. the function f changes a little. Imagine that the off equilibrium situation has been mapped to the factorial scheme ((1)). Then, some e_1, e_2 pairs disappear and some e_i, e_j pairs appear as one moves closer to equilibrium. The total number of particles and total energy remains constant. How does this affect the number of arrangements? Does the number stay constant, increase or decrease? One seems to reduce m_1 and m_2 and increase m_i and m_j . This, it seems, leads to a different value of ((1)). Imagine some e_i, e_j values that did not appear before, but are now present. This seems to lead to an increase in ((1)) i.e. as one moves away from large numbers of only e_1 and e_2 and distributes the energy more, one may obtain more arrangements. (For example, one may think of N particles with a total energy E and only one particle having all of this energy. As one distributes to different particles, more arrangements become possible. If too many particles have the same energy, say e_1 , there is a factor $m_1!$ which reduces the number of arrangements.) So far, no idea of scattering balance is considered. Note also that for the factorial arrangement, having an e_1 and e_2 next to each other means scattering of the two may occur.

Consider time reversal elastic scattering. This corresponds to a set of $g(f(e_i))$ values or m_i values in ((1)). Is this a set which maximizes the arrangements ((1))? Imagine it is not. Consider the arrangements ((1)) and consider e_1, e_2 pairs and a set e_3, e_4 such that $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. According to scattering balance, the number of e_1, e_2 pairs should match e_3, e_4 pairs. (Now not all e_1, e_2 will scatter into e_3, e_4 and vice versa (as other sets are available e.g. e_5, e_6), but the pair numbers should be the same. If there is a set e_5, e_6 such that $e_5+e_6=e_1+e_2$,

it should also have the same number of pairs.) Thus, changing some e_1, e_2 into e_3 and e_4 and the same number of e_3 and e_4 into e_1 and e_2 does not change the number of arrangements. Also, overall energy and particle number are conserved. It seems, however, that this is the same process as that carried out in the calculus of variations. In that process, one changes m_i values such that overall energy and particle number are conserved until a small change does not change the number of arrangements. Thus, time reversal elastic scattering balance does seem to be the same as maximization of factorial arrangements.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue one may obtain equilibrium distribution by only considering time reversal elastic scattering balances. We argued in (2), that these reactions may be mapped into the factorial scheme $M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots)$ where m_1 = the number of particles with energy e_1 in the Maxwell-Boltzmann picture. For more general cases, (fermions, bosons etc), m_1 is a measure of the number of reactions in which a particle with energy e_1 may participate. Thus, if an e_1 and e_2 appear next to each other in an arrangement of $((1))$, it means they may react. In this note, we argue that reaction balance is equivalent to maximizing $((1))$. Thus, the idea of maximizing scattering reactions (or particle arrangements in the Maxwell-Boltzmann picture) is not a new principle in nature, but is equivalent to a time reversal elastic scattering balance, which is a natural idea in the sense that if an e_1 and e_2 react to produce an e_3 and e_4 , there is the same probability for e_3 and e_4 to react and produce e_1 and e_2 , maintaining particle numbers $f(e_i)$, overall energy and the overall number of particles.

References

1. Huang, K. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) page 184
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Maximizing Number of Reactions versus Number of Particles with Energy e_i in Statistical Mechanics (preprint, zenodo, 2020)